

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**OVERVIEW OF ETIOLOGY AND CLINICAL MANAGEMENT
OF TINNITUS**

Ohoud Faisal Aburuzaiza

Article Received: June 2019**Accepted:** July 2019**Published:** August 2019**Abstract:**

Tinnitus is a common medical symptom that can be exhausting. Hearing loss, head injury, ototoxic medication, and depression are risk factors. In this review we discuss the main points of management, etiology and background information of tinnitus. We conducted a narrative review to identify studies with tinnitus etiology and treatment strategies among which were published up to June, 2019. Tinnitus is a perception of sound in proximity to the head in the absence of an outside source. The sound might be a buzzing, sounding, or hissing, although it can likewise seem like other noises.

Tinnitus is most typically connected with hearing loss, though it may be an offering signs and symptom of vascular or neurological irregularities. Once a serious underlying medical problem has been ruled out, treatment must be routed at the symptom itself, which badly hinders the quality of life in about 10 percent of patients with tinnitus.

Corresponding author:**Ohoud Faisal Aburuzaiza,**

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ohoud Faisal Aburuzaiza et al., **Overview Of Etiology And Clinical Management Of Tinnitus.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[08].

INTRODUCTION:

Tinnitus, originating from the Latin word 'tinnire' ('to ring'), is a perception of sound in proximity to the head with the absence of an exterior resource^[1]. It may be referred to as buzzing, sounding, roaring, whistling or hissing and can be variable and complex. Tinnitus might be periodic, continual or pulsatile, with the latter being at best annoying and frequently quite traumatic. It is approximated that about 15 - 20% of the globe populace experience tinnitus^{[2], [3]}. For around 25% of those impacted, the problem hinders daily task, with 1 - 3% of instances seriously influencing lifestyle^[3]. Extreme tinnitus is regularly associated with depression, anxiety and insomnia^{[3], [4]}.

Throughout the second fifty percent of the 20th century, numerous concepts for the aetiology of tinnitus were suggested and therapy modalities in the form of medicines and surgery were developed with varying degrees of success^[4]. Despite these advances, tinnitus continues to be a debilitating problem without definitive treatment, occasionally driving the patient to suicide^[4].

Tinnitus is a common medical symptom that can be exhausting. Hearing loss, head injury, ototoxic medication, and depression are risk factors. In this review we discuss the main points of management, etiology and background information of tinnitus.

METHODOLOGY:

We conducted a narrative review to identify studies with tinnitus etiology and treatment strategies among which were published up to June, 2019. Searched performed using electronic databases such Medline, and Embase. Following Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms were used by our search strategy; "tinnitus," "etiology," combined with "etiology OR Causes," and "Management OR Treatment".

DISCUSSION:

Classification and Etiology: Tinnitus can be categorized in 2 classifications. Objective tinnitus relates to generation of sound near the ear that, sometimes, can be listened to by the examiner using a stethoscope^[5]. Subjective tinnitus is the perception of sound in the lack of an acoustic stimulus and is heard just by the patient^[5].

Objective tinnitus is an unusual incident entailing an audible, pulsatile hum and can be caused by turbulent circulation through the carotid artery or jugular vein

^[6]. Highly vascular middle ear tumours (e.g. glomus jugulare tumors) and dural arteriovenous malformations may also cause objective tinnitus^[6].

Subjective tinnitus is far more usual and might occur with nearly any kind of ear ailment^[6]. Typical reasons consist of sensorineural hearing loss (e.g. acoustic injury), blockage of the ear canal by cerumen, infections (e.g. otitis media), Eustachian tube blockage and medications such as salicylates^[7]. Most of patients have "sensorineural" tinnitus, which is connected with hearing loss at the cochlea or cochlear nerve level^[7].

The table 1 reveals known danger elements for creating tinnitus and connected problems. The major risk factor is hearing loss, but this association is not simple or straightforward; some individuals with troublesome tinnitus have audiometrically typical hearing and, on the other hand, many people with hearing loss do not report tinnitus^{[8], [9]}. People who report high degrees of both occupational and recreational sound exposure are more likely to have tinnitus^[9].

Various other elements such as excessive weight, smoking cigarettes, alcohol consumption, previous head injuries, history of arthritis, and high blood pressure have been recommended as possible threat factors, and some outcomes have recommended a tiny genetic proneness^{[8], [9]}.

Numerous medications can set off ringing in the ears, including salicylates, quinine, aminoglycoside antibiotics, and several of the antineoplastic agents, especially the platinum-based drugs.

The problem can occur in association with numerous otological diseases, including otosclerosis, Ménière's disease, and vestibular schwannoma (acoustic neuroma). Tinnitus also has several comorbidities, particularly anxiety, anxiety, and dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint.

Decreased sound tolerance (hyperacusis) is a common coming with signs and symptom - defined as an aversion to loud noises, some degree of hyperacusis is kept in mind in 40% of patients with ringing in the ears, and up to 86% of patients that report hyperacusis likewise report tinnitus^[10].

Table 1. Known risk elements for establishing tinnitus and conditions associated with tinnitus signs and symptoms^{[5], [8], [9], [10]}.

Table 1. Known risk factors for developing tinnitus and conditions associated with tinnitus symptoms.

	Specific diseases or conditions
Otological, infectious	Otitis media, labyrinthitis, mastoiditis
Otological, neoplastic	Vestibular schwannoma, meningioma
Otological, labyrinthine	Sensorineural hearing loss, Ménière's disease, vestibular vertigo
Otological, other	Impacted cerumen, otosclerosis, presbycusis, noise exposure
Neurological	Meningitis, migraine, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy
Traumatic	Head or neck injury, loss of consciousness
Orofacial	Temporomandibular joint disorder
Cardiovascular	Hypertension
Rheumatological	Rheumatoid arthritis
Immune-mediated	Systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic sclerosis
Endocrine and metabolic	Diabetes mellitus, hyperinsulinaemia, hypothyroidism, hormonal changes during pregnancy
Psychological	Anxiety, depression, emotional trauma
Ototoxic medications	Analgesics, antibiotics, antineoplastic drugs, corticosteroids, diuretics, immunosuppressive drugs, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

Diagnosis: A stepwise decision-tree technique for clinical tinnitus management could be utilized. Fundamental diagnostic steps are recommended for all patients and should consist of a thorough medical history (panel), assessment of tinnitus seriousness (figure 1), medical ear checkup, and audiological measurement of tinnitus and hearing function.

History: The patient's medical history guides the differential diagnosis. Key areas of inquiry include previous background of acoustic injury, occupational sound exposure, or ototoxic drug usage. Tinnitus can be unilateral or bilateral, low pitched (buzzing or humming) or high pitched (buzzing or hissing), and pulsatile (pulse synchronous or pulse asynchronous) or nonpulsatile. The clinician can figure out if the tinnitus is bothersome or nonbothersome (ie, the patient is aware of the tinnitus, but it does not influence his or her day-to-day activity or functioning). Relevant symptoms, such as hearing loss and vertigo, are sought in addition to focal neurologic signs and symptoms.

Health examination: Physical exam can be directed based upon the working differential medical diagnosis but is normally restricted to cranial nerve examination and otoscopy, looking for signs of infection, eardrum perforation, or middle ear tumours. Auscultation for bruits is performed over the neck, mastoid, and preauricular locations for patients with pulsatile tinnitus.

Audiologic testing: All patients with tinnitus need to be described an audiologist to undergo an audiological evaluation to help figure out acoustic function and the presence of any hearing loss ^[11]. An audiologist can additionally quantify the tinnitus viewed by the patient via dedicated tinnitus testing. Specifically, 4 parameters are gauged, consisting of pitch, loudness, mask ability, and residual inhibition ^[12].

Laboratory testing and imaging: Laboratory testing in tinnitus is typically not shown. For a lot of patients who provide with bilateral nonpulsatile signs, we recommend against regular imaging. For patients with pulsatile tinnitus, a magnetic resonance angiogram and venogram of the mind and neck is one of the most useful tests to eliminate vascular abnormalities. For patients with nonpulsatile unilateral ringing in the ears and normal otoscopy findings, or asymmetrical SNHL, a referral to an otolaryngologist or screening noncontrast magnetic resonance imaging of the internal auditory canals is advised ^[13].

Recommendation to an otolaryngologist: When tinnitus is pulsatile or unilateral in nature, or abnormal otoscopy findings are kept in mind, referral to an otolaryngologist is suggested to dismiss hidden conditions ^[13]. Imaging can be bought before the referral, if suitable.

Figure 1. Assessment of tinnitus severity Modified and translated from Biesinger and colleagues ^[14].

Clinical management: Therapies for management of tinnitus along with specific treatment of underlying or co-occurring abnormal adjustments include counselling, cognitive behavioral therapy, sound therapy, listening to aids, cochlear implants, pharmacotherapy, and brain excitement. Proof degrees for a lot of therapy strategies are low, which goes to the very least partly as a result of the heterogeneity of tinnitus, the difficulties in the evaluation of tinnitus, significant placebo effects, and reduced methodological high quality of lots of treatment trials. The demand for consistency in evaluation and result measurement is progressively recognized as an establishing consider contrasts of treatment effectiveness.

PSYCHOLOGICAL TREATMENTS:

Counselling and psychoeducation: For the most part tinnitus cannot be treated, but some methods can aid accomplish habituation to the phantom noise. To help individuals cope with tinnitus, psychoeducation--normally called counselling in the context of tinnitus treatment- is a vital part of all management options and could be regarded adequate therapy oftentimes. Counselling makes up provision of information, suggestions, and empowerment of patients with tinnitus to assist attain habituation to the perception of the phantom sound, and to better deal with its possible consequences, such as emotional distress, sleeping troubles, loss of focus, interest problems, and disruption to their individual, occupational, and social

lives. By giving information, counselling goals to assist people to comprehend their tinnitus, to demystify the condition, and to remedy false beliefs. Ultimately, counselling is very important to make sure compliance with treatment techniques by providing the necessary information concerning sensible goals of the various treatment interventions. Coaching is an essential part of the management of every patient with tinnitus, however controlled research studies to approximate its effectiveness are not available and are difficult to do.

Tinnitus retraining therapy: Tinnitus retraining treatment is a distinct mix of counselling and sound therapy, which is founded on the assumption that the neurophysiological correlate of tinnitus is uncommon activity and connectivity of auditory and non-auditory main nervous circuits ^[15]. The goal of tinnitus retraining treatment is to attain habituation by training or counselling for reclassification of the tinnitus signal to the group of neutral stimuli, and noise therapy to reduce the stamina of the tinnitus signal. Whereas some research studies recommend beneficial effects, a Cochrane meta-analysis stated that as a result of the absence of premium randomized clinical tests, no final conclusions concerning the efficacy of tinnitus retraining treatment can be attracted ^{[16],[17]}.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy: Cognitive-behavioral interventions are the best investigated psychotherapeutic methods for managing tinnitus.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy intends to decrease the tinnitus-related handicap by modifying maladaptive cognitive, emotional, and behavioral responses to ringing in the ears by means of cognitive restructuring and behavioral alteration. The major elements of cognitive-behavioral therapy include psychoeducation, relaxation training, mindfulness-based training, attention-control strategies, imagery training, and exposure to difficult situations, which are utilized to change maladaptive actions. Results of a meta-analysis in which eight regulated tests including 468 participants were assessed revealed clear evidence for an improvement in quality of life and decrease of depression scores after therapy, when cognitive behavior modification was compared to no therapy or an additional intervention, even if cognitive-behavioral treatment did not reduce tinnitus volume [19]. In a large randomized clinical test, a multidisciplinary tipped care approach including counselling and aspects of cognitive-behavioral treatment and tinnitus retraining treatment showed considerable benefit in tinnitus intensity, tinnitus disability, and health-related quality of life compared to normal therapy [18]. There are no long-term follow-up information from regulated tests [19].

AUDITORY STIMULATION:

Sound therapy: Both environmental and customized sound generators are utilized in the therapy of tinnitus. Environmental sound generators are little gadgets that play noises such as sea waves, creeks, waterfalls, rain, or white noise, which are meant to be relaxing and to minimize the perception of the tinnitus sound. The principle of sound generation is that the masking noise ought to be regarded as much less troubling than the tinnitus sound. Customized sound generators resemble routine hearing aids and are used behind the ear. They generally create a broad band sound, the frequency composition and loudness of which can be adapted to either partly or totally mask the tinnitus. Hearing aids with incorporated noise generators are also available. Even though sound stimulation is frequently made use of, the proof for its effectiveness based upon controlled research studies is insufficient [20].

Hearing aids: Hearing aids represent another kind of sound therapy that is generally beneficial to tinnitus patients with substantial hearing loss [21]. Hearing aids are designed to improve the audibility of speech and to amplify ambient sounds. Amplification of speech diverts interest far from tinnitus, and amplification of various other ambient noises serves to partially mask tinnitus. Hearing aids are not proper for those with hearing loss confined to above 6 kHz, since most listening devices have actually limited high-frequency

amplification capabilities [22]. The use of hearing aids can permanently minimize the neural activity in charge of tinnitus generation and perception, and normally stands for the first intervention for patients with hearing impairment [21], [22]. Numerous hearing-impaired patients have typical or near-normal hearing at low frequencies, and typical environmental noises contain a significant amount of energy below 200 Hz, which gives continuous sound stimulation and therefore aids to avoid troubles associated with increased gain in the auditory system. Consequently, it is vital to fit hearing aids with open molds in the outside ear to prevent obstructing these low frequencies [21].

Cochlear implants: In patients with bilateral profound sensorineural hearing loss and tinnitus, a significant suppression of ringing in the ears has been reported after hearing was restored by cochlear implant [23]. Cochlear implants are additionally beneficial in patients with unilateral profound deafness with concomitant ipsilateral incapacitating tinnitus [23]. Thus, there is increasing proof that cochlear implants offer substantial lasting tinnitus suppression in patients with serious sensorineural hearing loss by restoration of input to the central auditory system.

Individualized sound stimulation: Three major strategies have been made use of in individualized sound stimulation. One approach is based upon the notion that the tinnitus spectrum fills in the areas of hearing loss, and that an enriched acoustic setting that makes up for the hearing loss can get rid of the neural correlates of ringing in the ears in animals [24]. Auditory stimulation consisting of music with a separately adjusted frequency spectrum to make up for the specific hearing loss is combined with counselling in a structured rehabilitation program in the Neuraminic Tinnitus Treatment. In initial medical research studies this treatment seems to be more effective than the mix of counselling with broad-band noise excitement [25]. However, in a controlled study music independently tailored to compensate for hearing loss did not offer any advantage, whereas overcompensation of the hearing loss aggravated the tinnitus [26]. A second individualized auditory excitement technique makes use of music stimulation with the frequency range around the tinnitus gotten rid of from the regularity spectrum [27]. A pilot study in an extremely selected sample of patients with tonal tinnitus showed a little however significant decrease in tinnitus volume and auditory-evoked cortical activity after 1 year of day-to-day stimulation with tailor-made notched music compared to a control problem [27]. A

third strategy has been suggested in which personalized auditory stimuli are presented as short tones above and below the ringing in the ears regularity as a brand-new approach to renormalize tinnitus related neuronal synchrony. A pilot research showed significant reductions of tinnitus volume and aggravation, and normalization of uncommon oscillatory activity by this so-called coordinated reset stimulation compared with a control group [28]. All these techniques still have to be considered as experimental up until the preliminary results are verified in large randomized controlled tests.

Auditory perceptual training: Numerous auditory training procedures have been developed with the objective to renormalize tinnitus-related neuroplastic adjustments. Training procedures include regularity discrimination training, intensity discrimination training, and auditory object recognition and localization [29]. Every one of these training treatments have actually been done within and outside the ringing in the ears frequency region, and as active training treatments requiring behavior and passive feedbacks with background sounds. Although results of these studies suggest some promise for auditory training in ringing in the ears treatment, final conclusions about the efficiency of auditory perceptual training are not feasible as a result of the low technical quality of many studies [30].

Pharmacological treatments: Some pharmacologic treatments can be advantageous when given in combination with conservative management. Exogenous melatonin has been shown to improve tinnitus symptoms, and specifically enhances rest [32]. Current tinnitus standards suggest against the routine use of antidepressant, anticonvulsant, or anxiolytic medication for bothersome tinnitus [31]. Nonetheless, for patients with pre-existing anxiety and depression, making use of tricyclic antidepressants and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors has been revealed to be reliable in taking care of tinnitus signs and symptoms, reducing the level of annoyance [31], [32].

Brain stimulation: Based on awareness showing tinnitus-related abnormalities in distinctive areas of the central auditory system, potentially linked to high spontaneous neuronal activity, brain stimulation has been investigated as a method to decrease neuronal activity [36].

Repeated transcranial magnetic excitation uses non-invasive electromagnetic induction to generate weak electrical currents in the brain, hence reducing neural excitability. A systematic review analyzed five trials

that contrasted this technique with a control, all with non-navigated coil localization [33].

The searching for showed minimal assistance for use of low-frequency transcranial magnetic stimulation to minimize tinnitus volume or improve quality of life. Each test described making use of a different device that provided different waveforms at different stimulation rates; interpretation of the findings is difficult, because the various stimulation protocols were differentially useful for tinnitus. No significant adverse results were reported in any of the trials; however, the lasting safety and security of this treatment is unknown.

In numerous research studies patients with motion disorders and comorbid ringing in the ears that undertook deep brain stimulation for the movement condition reported a reduction in tinnitus volume when the implant was switched on, without influencing hearing [34], [35]. One study separated the benefit to stimulation of area LC in the caudate nucleus [35]. This brain region is not part of the classic auditory path, so these initial monitorings call for further investigation.

Surgical management: Surgical management is extremely rarely utilized in patients with tinnitus and is just used for treatable hidden reasons [36]. These can consist of the medical resection of acoustic neuroma or other brainstem or cerebellopontine angle tumors and lesions, endolymphatic sac shunting for Ménière illness, or stapedectomy for otosclerosis. Tensor tympani and stapedius myoclonus disorders are additionally correctable with surgical procedure by sectioning the influenced muscles [36].

CONCLUSION:

Tinnitus is a perception of sound in proximity to the head in the absence of an outside source. The sound might be a buzzing, sounding, or hissing, although it can likewise seem like other noises.

Tinnitus is most typically connected with hearing loss, though it may be an offering sign and symptom of vascular or neurological irregularities. Once a serious underlying medical problem has been ruled out, treatment must be routed at the symptom itself, which badly hinders the quality of life in about 10 percent of patients with tinnitus.

Family physicians play the primary role in handling patients with tinnitus and are well situated to deal with both the physiologic and the emotional symptoms. As tinnitus is very common, helping patients manage the signs and symptoms with traditional procedures and reassurance can prove to have the best results.

REFERENCE:

1. Crummer RW, Hassan GA. Diagnostic approach to tinnitus. *Am Fam Physician*. 2004;69(1):120–126. doi: 10.1017/S1755146300090041.
2. Axelsson A, Ringdahl A. Tinnitus—a study of its prevalence and characteristics. *Br J Audiol*. 1989;23(1):53–62. doi: 10.3109/03005368909077819.
3. Claussen CF, Rakel & Bope: *Conn's Current Therapy*. 60. Philadelphia: Elsevier Inc.; 2008.
4. Lockwood AH. Tinnitus. *Neurol Clin*. 2005;23(3):893–900. doi: 10.1016/j.ncl.2005.01.007.
5. Ahmad N, Seidman M. Tinnitus in the older adult: epidemiology, pathophysiology and treatment options. *Drugs Aging*. 2004;21(5):297–305. doi: 10.2165/00002512-200421050-00002.
6. Schleuning AJ., 2nd Management of the patient with tinnitus. *Med Clin North Am*. 1991;75(6):1225–1237.
7. Davis A, El Rafaie A. Epidemiology of tinnitus. In: Tyler RS *Tinnitus handbook*. Singular, Thomson Learning, San Diego, CA; 2000: 1-23.
8. Nondahl DM, Cruickshanks KJ, Huang G-H et al. Tinnitus and its risk factors in the Beaver Dam Offspring Study. *Int J Audiol*. 2011; 50: 313-320.
9. Saldanha AD, Hilgenberg PB, Pinto LM, Conti PC. Are temporomandibular disorders and tinnitus associated?. *Cranio*. 2012; 30: 166-171.
10. Henry JA, Zaugg TL, Myers PJ, Kendall CJ. Progressive tinnitus management. *Clinical handbook for audiologists*. San Diego, CA: Plural Publishing Inc; 2010.
11. Henry JA, Meikle MB. Psychoacoustic measures of tinnitus. *J Am Acad Audiol*. 2000;11(3):138–55.
12. Fortnum H, O'Neill C, Taylor R, Lenthall R, Nikolopoulos T, Lightfoot G, et al. The role of magnetic resonance imaging in the identification of suspected acoustic neuroma: a systematic review of clinical and cost effectiveness and natural history. *Health Technol Assess*. 2009;13(18):iii–iv, ix–xi, 1–154.
13. Biesinger E, Heiden C, Greimel V, Lendle T, Hoing R, Albegger K. Strategies in ambulatory treatment of tinnitus. *HNO* 1998; 46: 157–69.
14. Jastreboff PJ. Tinnitus retraining therapy. *Prog Brain Res* 2007; 166: 415–23.
15. Bauer CA, Brozoski TJ. Effect of tinnitus retraining therapy on the loudness and annoyance of tinnitus: a controlled trial. *Ear Hear* 2011; 32: 145–55.
16. Phillips JS, McFerran D. Tinnitus retraining therapy (TRT) for tinnitus. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2010; 3: CD007330.
17. Jastreboff PJ. Phantom auditory perception (tinnitus): mechanisms of generation and perception. *Neurosci Res* 1990; 8: 221–54.
18. Cima RFF, Maes IH, Joore MA, et al. Specialised treatment based on cognitive behaviour therapy versus usual care for tinnitus: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 2012; 379: 1951–59.
19. Hobson J, Chisholm E, El Refaie A. Sound therapy (masking) in the management of tinnitus in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2010; 12: CD006371.
20. Folmer RL, Martin WH, Shi Y, Edlefsen LL. Tinnitus sound therapy. In: Tyler RS, editor. *Tinnitus treatment*. New York: Thieme; 2006. pp. 176–186.
21. Searchfield GD. Hearing aids and tinnitus. In: Tyler RS, editor. *Tinnitus treatment*. New York: Thieme; 2006. pp. 161–175.
22. Van de Heyning P, Vermeire K, Diebl M, Nopp P, Anderson I, De Ridder D. Incapacitating unilateral tinnitus in single-sided deafness treated by cochlear implantation. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol* 2008; 117: 645–52.
23. Norena AJ, Eggermont JJ. Enriched acoustic environment after noise trauma abolishes neural signs of tinnitus. *Neuroreport* 2006; 17: 559–63.
24. Davis PB, Paki B, Hanley PJ. Neuromonics Tinnitus Treatment: third clinical trial. *Ear Hear* 2007; 28: 242–59.
25. Vanneste S, van Dongen M, De Vree B, et al. Does enriched acoustic environment in humans abolish chronic tinnitus clinically and electrophysiologically? A double blind placebo controlled study. *Hear Res* 2012; 296: 141–48.
26. Okamoto H, Stracke H, Stoll W, Pantev C. Listening to tailor-made notched music reduces tinnitus loudness and tinnitus-related auditory cortex activity. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2010; 107: 1207–10.
27. Tass PA, Adamchic I, Freund HJ, von Stackelberg T, Hauptmann C. Counteracting tinnitus by acoustic coordinated reset neuromodulation. *Restor Neurol Neurosci* 2012; 30: 137–59.
28. Roberts LE, Bosnyak DJ. Auditory training in tinnitus. In: Moller A, Langguth B, De Ridder D, Kleinjung T, eds. *Textbook of tinnitus*. New York: Springer, 2011; 563–73.
29. Hoare DJ, Stacey PC, Hall DA. The efficacy of auditory perceptual training for tinnitus: a systematic review. *Ann Behav Med* 2010; 40: 313–24.

30. Tunkel DE, Bauer CA, Sun GH, Rosenfeld RM, Chandrasekhar SS, Cunningham ER, Jr, et al. Clinical practice guideline: tinnitus. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2014;151(2 Suppl):S1–40.
31. Megwalu UC, Finnell JE, Piccirillo JF. The effects of melatonin on tinnitus and sleep. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2006;134(2):210–3.
32. Meng Z, Liu S, Zheng Y, Phillips JS. Repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation for tinnitus. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2011; 10 (CD007946)
33. Shi Y, Burchiel KJ, Anderson VC, Martin WH. Deep brain stimulation effects in patients with tinnitus. *Otolaryngology Head Neck Surg.* 2009; 141: 285-287.
34. Cheung SW, Larson PS. Tinnitus modulation by deep brain stimulation in locus of caudate neurons (area LC). *Neuroscience.* 2010; 169: 1768-1778.
35. Eggermont J, Roberts L. The neuroscience of tinnitus. *Trends Neurosci.* 2004; 27: 676-682.
36. Bhimrao SK, Masterson L, Baguley D. Systematic review of management strategies for middle ear myoclonus. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2012;146(5):698–706. Epub 2012 Jan 18.